

The Relevance of the Bhagavad Gita A Comparative Exploration Across Faiths and Philosophies

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Abstract

Bhagwad gita is also known as Gitopnishad. Gita means song and Upanishad means sitting near teacher, here the teacher is Lord Krishna. But when we hear or named this sacred book 'Bhagwad gita' we always think that this is Hindu granth. Even lord Krishna never used the word Hindu in this song (gita), only the word "Sanatana" is used which means "eternal or which have no beginning and no end". Through using the word Hindu for this, we make the limitations on the sacredness and transcendental knowledge of lord Krishna. Actually the message of Bhagwad gita is not limited; this also have some similarities with other religions philosophies and also applicable for this modern and scientific world. There are many songs or gita's in Mahabharata but Bhagwad gita is most important because it clarifies all the doubt in human mind. The discussion between Arjuna and lord Krishna is very pure and transcendental. Lord Krishna as the charioteer follows the order of Arjuna. As it is mentioned in the following verse.[1]

Keywords Bhagavad Gita, Faiths, Philosophies.

Introduction

सेनयोरुभयोर्मध्ये रथं स्थापय मेऽच्युत || 21||

Arjuna said: O infallible one, please draw my chariot between the two armies

Arjuna through respecting the Krishna said oh infallible one or Achyuta. Krishna, who is superior than Arjuna from both sides that is spiritually (because he is lord) and materially. But not showing superiority over Arjuna, they serve Arjuna and follow his order[2]. Not due to any materialistic reason, but only due to love and respect. This love between Arjuna and lord Krishna is very pure and transcendental.

Objective of study

The objective of this paper is to study the comparative exploration across faiths and philosophies in the relevance of the Bhagavad Gita.

Review of Literature

There are many literature reviewed for this paper which have been discussed through out the paper.

Main Text

Bhagwad gita mainly focuses yoga's like karma yoga and bhakti yoga. According to Karma yoga, one should have to do work without thinking or predicting the result. Because desire of the better result, sometime causes suffering, and if you are not doing your karma or work, you do not have right to desiring about good result. Krishna also declares that work in devotional service is better than renunciation of works. [3]

Bhagwad gita also explains how can we achieve god? Actually for achieving God, we can only love them. Love as friend, as parents or child, even as lover. The love of supreme person is not by high position or though richness because for god, a rich person is not the one who has the most, but is one who needs the least.; we have to control our eight senses and love god as the supreme destination because without love we cannot achieve god. As mentioned in Bhagwad gita 10.14

सर्वमेतदृतं मन्ये यन्मां वदसि केशव ।
न हि ते भगवन्व्यक्तितं विदुर्देवा न दानवाः ॥ 14॥

“O Krishna, I totally accept as truth all that you have told me. Neither the gods nor demons, o lord know thy personality.”

As explained by Prabhupada[4], “Arjuna herein confirms that persons of faithless and demonic nature cannot understand Krishna. He is not even known by the demigods, so what to speak of the so-called scholars of this modern world?”.....

God wants only surrender and if we do not love God then how can we surrender unto him. It is also mentioned in bible:[5]

“Jesus replied: ‘Love the lord your God with all your heart and with all your soul and with all your mind.’ Again it is mentioned that:[6] “The fool has said in his heart, there is no god”

In modern world, the concept of faith is also missing in humans, not only for god but also for other beings. Sometime we claim that we have full faith on our parents, children, wife or friend; but actually that's not faith because anytime, anywhere, a single misunderstanding helps us to forget all memorable and lovable moments with her or him. As written by Ahmed for modern youth: “Of course, if he is good by nature, he may believe in God, but does so without full faith and sincerity and that too is conditional upon his own success. If his desires are fulfilled he turns to God, if not, he turns to Satan”. But why this situation creates? Because we don't know the truth and this truth is told either by spiritual master or god himself. [7] The spiritual master helps us to knowing about god. When we know who is god, then we get faith and this faith creates a transcendental love between the god and his devotee.[8] In Bhagwad gita it is said that

ये तु धर्म्यामृतमिदं यथोक्तं पर्युपासते ।
श्रद्धधाना मत्परमा भक्तास्तेऽतीव मे प्रियाः ॥ 20॥

“He who follows this imperishable path of devotional service and who completely engages himself with faith, making me the supreme goal, is very, very dear to me”,[9] it is also mentioned in bible:[10] “god is spirit, and his worshipers must worship in the spirit and in truth.” The main aim of human life is to engage in the worship of supreme personality of godhead. If we do not love god that means we are wasting our life. It is also mentioned in Quran:[11] “Jinn and Man created for worship of Allah.”

Concept of Varna Aashram

But some people believe that the Supreme person discriminate the people on the basis of birth through varna system and especially shudras do not have right to worship the lord. As it mention in Purusha sukta of Rig Veda:[12]

ब्राह्मणोऽस्य मुखमासीद् बाहू राजन्यः कृतः ।
ऊरू तदस्य यद्वैश्यः पद्भ्यां शूद्रो अजायत ॥१२॥

Brahmna was his mouth, Kshatriya was arms, Vaishyas were thighs and shudras were born from his feet.

This is said that occupation of these varnas was fixed and they can't change their occupation. This rigidity of varna system was challenged by great personalities like mahatma Buddha and Mahavira Jain. Bhagwad gita also claims the rigidity of this hierarchical Varna system and supports occupation by three modes of nature and not by birth. As it is mentioned in[13]

चातुर्वर्ण्यं मया सृष्टं गुणकर्मविभागशः ।
तस्य कर्तारमपि मां विद्ध्यकर्तारमव्ययम् ॥ 13॥

According to the three modes of material nature and the work ascribed to them, the four divisions of human society were created by Me. And, although I am the creator of this system, you should know that I am yet the non-doer, being unchangeable.

Again it is mentioned[14]

ब्राह्मणक्षत्रियविशां शूद्राणां च परन्तप ।
कर्माणि प्रविभक्तानि स्वभावप्रभवैर्गुणैः ॥ 41॥

Brāhmaṇas, kṣatriyas, vaiśyas and śūdras are distinguished by their qualities of work, O chastiser of the enemy, in accordance with the modes of nature.

These verses show that philosophy of Bhagwad gita is against the evil practices and laws of Hinduism. There are many religions which are against the caste system but now they are divided into various castes. Even in India at present, this varna system is prevailed by birth in many parts.

There is also some references were founded in Mahabharata (Vana parva, chapter 180) [15]

If the characteristics of Brahmana are found in a Shudra and not in a Brahmana, that Shudra not be known as Shudra and that Brahmana should not be known as Brahmana.

According to teachings of Bhagwad gita, God never creates discrimination; it is the men, who want to show their superiority over others for their self interest. Brahmins believes that they are more pure than shudras. But this is believed that “*janamna jayte Shudra*” that is from birth everyone is Shudra, because all are born from squalor. But forgetting all these things, Brahmins continuously follow this hierarchical varna system Lord Krishna believes that how can he discriminate one soul from another. All the souls have same size and qualities. As written by Singh, for proving that the soul is the proof of the existence of god. “The soul (Aatma) or the divine light in us is a reflection of god (Parmaatma). It may be compared to a tiny molecule (soul) of water from the sea (god). It can be explained by the analogy of the multiple images of the same person in different mirrors; each mirror (human being) carries a reflection (soul) of the person (god). Soul is there because of god, it is not independent reality without god. Just as an image is an evidence of the existence of a real thing, in the same way we human beings are evidence of the fact that god exists.”[16] Like the god, the soul never destroyed. As it is mentioned in following verse[17]

नैनं छिन्दन्ति शस्त्राणि नैनं दहति पावकः ।
न चैनं क्लेदयन्त्यापो न शोषयति मारुतः ॥ 23॥

“The soul can never cut into pieces by any weapon, nor can he burned by fire, nor moistened by water, nor withered by the wind”.

Modern scholars are trying to know about the concept of soul, but they will not be succeed because as it is written in Quran[18]

“And they ask you (O Muhammad saw) concerning the Ruh (the spirit); say: The Ruh (The spirit): it is one of the things, the knowledge of which is only with my Lord. And of knowledge, you (mankind) have been given only a little.”

Today, the universal teachings of Bhagwad gita fully declined because we always studied political, social aspects but never study the teachings. Modern education fully supports the factual and scientific knowledge but they don't support the science of god, which are his teachings. This is the real knowledge; actually through modern education we are getting only the information not knowledge. The real knowledge is self realization and realization of god. Modern education system claims that Bhagwad gita cannot be applicable for modern world but lord Krishna declares that

न त्वेवाहं जातु नासं न त्वं नेमे जनाधिपा ।
न चैव न भविष्यामः सर्वे वयमतः परम् ॥ 12॥

“Never was there a time when I did not exist, nor you, nor all these kings; nor in the future shall any of us cease to be”.

Time has changed but lord and his philosophical teachings will never change. There is no power exists which can cease the soul and the supreme soul. It is mentioned in bible that:[19] “the grass withers and the flowers fall, but the word of our God endures forever.” Like this, Guru Nanak dev Ji in his bani also explains that:[20]

“Only one, who is not subject evaluation has a permanent place. The sky, the earth will perish but God is eternal”.

This materialistic world is actually an artificial world. The real destination is the supreme destination and which can be only achieved through the self realization and through pure love for god. After the self realization, one can see god everywhere, in every being. As said by lord Krishna:

यो मां पश्यति सर्वत्र सर्वं च मयि पश्यति ।
तस्याहं न प्रणश्यामि स च मे न प्रणश्यति ॥ 30॥

For one who sees Me everywhere and sees everything in Me, I am never lost, nor is he ever lost to Me.

One who realizes this truth realizes that God is omnipresent, they are present in each atom but they are disappeared in modern world because some clever people are trying to find questions from answers. They don't know, everything directly or indirectly is originated from God or a part of God but they are trying to find stupid questions like who created God? Bhagwad gita refers that human indriyas have some limits like limits of eyes, limit of lifting weights, limit of walk; When we think about who created god, then we think about time i.e. me, me from my father, my father from my grandfather and so on... then universe, universe from god and god? that is the limit of brain. Only the prophets and messengers know this truth because they have holy-spirit and self-controlled senses. The apostle Peter explained it this way:[21] “Prophecy never had its origin in the human will, but prophets, though human, spoke from God as they were carried along by the Holy Spirit”.

Nowadays, people claims that through loving other people they will reach to heaven. They call their selfishness or self interest as love, but that's not love. This is false attraction. We can differentiate love and attraction; Love is for others welfare without considering our own self interests and on the other side in attraction, we always take our self interest; for example a bird in a cage is attraction and bird in sky is love. In bhagavad gita Arjuna loves his family, his teacher as well as his upcoming generation. He said[22] that “O Krishna, how can I counterattack with arrows in battle men like Bhishma and Dronna, who are worthy of my worship”. Krishna is smiling at that time[23] because Arjuna caring or loving those teachers who have forgotten their own teachings and they were also present at the time of Draupadi Cheer Haran. Krishna tells Arjuna that whom he is considering living humans, they are already dead. Krishna were trying to realize Arjuna that I want to do work through you and in this he is not taking Arjuna's help, but this is Arjuna's karma or duty to fight[24] and he can win the war in few seconds if he desires about this.. It is also said that

पुरुषः स परः पार्थ भक्त्या लभ्यस्त्वनन्यया ।
यस्यान्तःस्थानि भूतानि येन सर्वमिदं ततम् ॥ 22॥ [25]

“The Supreme Personality of Godhead, who is greater than all, is attainable by unalloyed devotion. Although He is present in His abode, He is all-pervading, and everything is situated within Him”.

Bhagwad gita also explains that one's ambition led to the suffering. The human nature changed like a climate, according to their desires[26]. As said by Krishna

यदृच्छालाभसन्तुष्टो द्वन्द्वातीतो विमत्सरः ।
समः सिद्धावसिद्धौ च कृत्वापि न निबध्यते ॥ 22॥

He who is satisfied with gain which comes of its own accord, who is free from duality and does not envy, who is steady both in success and failure, is never entangled, although performing actions.

God only loves the "Samabhava" people; "Samabhava" means whose mind is constant. Who is steady always and performed all his action for the supreme one and not for their own self interest. At present, there are many people who controls their senses but their mind dwells on these senses, according to Bhagwad gita,

Conclusion

In the last, author wants to conclude his words after saying that Bhagavad-gita is the one of the best way through which a man is able to fulfill the aim of life. The holy gita is the first revelation from God. Through this, we realized that if God is eternal, then his teachings are also eternal. We know that modern science is developing in a excellent way but through this development, we can't say that we will not suffer. We will suffer; either we are living in moon or in earth. Even sometimes, with the development of science and technology some new problems arises like pollution, nuclear famine, global warming etc. but the main aim of Bhagavad-gita and Indian philosophy is "Loka Samastha Sukhino Bhavanthu" that means "all beings be happy". According to modern scholars, man is a rational being but what is the benefit of this rationality. We are wasting our life in eating, sleeping, and in rearing of children and in caring of family. But all these things are also done by animals. We have our rational mind only for knowing that who is the Supreme personality of Godhead, and how to leave this cycle of rebirth. For this, we have to love God and surrender unto him. Without Supreme person, every person is like a animal. The simple message of Bhagavad-gita is

"Love God & be happy"...

References

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7. Hadrat Mirza Ghulam Ahmad, *The philosophy of teachings of Islam, Islam international publications Ltd. 2010*
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Endnote

1. Bhagavad-gita chapter 1, verse 21
2. Krishna in Bhagavad-gita chapter 1, verse 24 follow order and move the chariot between the two armies.
3. As in Bhagavad-gita chapter 5 verse 2
4. Prabhupada, bhagavad-gita As it is, pg 537
5. Matthew 22:37
6. Psalm 14:1
7. Krishna in Bhagavad-gita chapter 4 verse 34 also said that "just try to learn the truth by approaching a spiritual master"
8. In Bhagwad gita chapter 12, the methods for achieving god are mentioned in which the best method is love and surrender.
9. Bhagavad-gita chapter 12 verse 20
10. John 4:24
11. Al quran 51:56
12. Rig Veda 10.1.13
13. Bhagavad-gita chapter 4 verse 13
14. Bhagavad-gita chapter 18 verse 41
15. sudre tu yad bhavel-laksma, dvije tac ca na vidyate, na vai sudro bhavec chudro, brahmano na ca brahmana
16. G. Singh, A brief introduction to the Sikh faith, pp 16
17. Bhagavad- gita chapter 2 verse 23
18. Quran chapter 17 Al-Isra verse 85
19. Isaiah 40:8
20. ਮੁਕਾਮੁ ਤਿਸ ਨੋ ਆਖੀਐ ਜਿਸੁ ਸਿਸਿ ਨ ਹੋਵੀ ਲੇਖੁ ॥ ਅਸਮਾਨੁ ਧਰਤੀ ਚਲਸੀ ਮੁਕਾਮੁ ਓਹੀ ਏਕੁ ॥੭॥

21. 2 Peter 1:21

22. Bhagavad-gita chapter 2 verse 4 mentioned "katham bhīṣmam ahaṁ sankhye droṇaṁ cha madhusūdana

iṣhubhiḥ pratiyotsyāmi pūjārḥāvāri-sūdana"

23. In Bhagavad-gita chapter 2 verse 10 krishna smiling in midst of both the army.

24. It is mentioned in bhagavad-gita chapter 11 verse 33 "therefore get up and prepare to fight. After conquering your enemies you will enjoy a flourishing kingdom. They are already put to death by My arrangement, and you, O Savyasācin, can be but an instrument in the fight.

25. Bhagavad-gita chapter 8 verse 22

26. Mahatma Buddha in his most famous teachings known as four noble truth also said that 1. Suffering; 2. Suffering is caused by desire; 3. If we stop our desire suffering will be stopped; 4. To end the desires follow this eight fold path or Ashtantiga marg or eight fold is also mention in Bhagavad-gita chapter 6 verse 3 "For one who is a neophyte in the eightfold yoga system, work is said to be the means; and for one who has already attained to yoga, cessation of all material activities is said to be the means".

27. In Bhagavad-gita chapter 3 verse 6 Krishna used the term "Mithyachari".